

Title

Impact of pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) on the risk of bacterial sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among cisgender women: a systematic review

Authors

Vasiliki Papageorgiou¹, vasiliki.papageorgiou17@imperial.ac.uk

Erica Crittendon¹, erica.crittendon17@imperial.ac.uk

Dr Bethan Davies², bethan.davies06@imperial.ac.uk

Professor Helen Ward¹, h.ward@imperial.ac.uk

¹ NIHR Imperial BRC Patient Experience Research Centre, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology, Imperial College London

² UK Small Area Health Statistics Unit, Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Imperial College London

Contact

Vasiliki Papageorgiou¹, vasiliki.papageorgiou17@imperial.ac.uk

Amendments

1 Introduction

1.1 Rationale

It is estimated that women aged 15 and over account for approximately 42% of new human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections, each year, globally.¹ In sub-Saharan Africa, where the disease is most prevalent, women constitute of 56% of the people living with HIV.²

The daily use of oral pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) with tenofovir/emtricitabine has demonstrated effectiveness in the prevention of HIV acquisition amongst multiple populations, including men who have sex with men (MSM) and heterosexual men and women.^{3 4} The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that oral PrEP should be offered to populations with an incidence of HIV of at least 3 per 100 person-years, in the absence of PrEP; these individuals are provisionally defined as being at a 'substantial risk' of HIV infection.^{5 6} Estimates indicate that approximately 380,000 people are currently enrolled to PrEP globally, with over 59% based in North America and 27% in sub-Saharan Africa.⁷

There is an increased, yet inconclusive, evidence-base exploring the association of PrEP uptake with 'risk compensation' or reported sexual risk behaviour (e.g. condomless sex, multiple partners) and the incidence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), which focuses primarily on MSM.⁸⁻¹¹ Some randomised control trials have reported no increase in STIs, whereas less controlled environments such as open-label or demonstration projects have reported increased STI incidence.^{3 9 12 13} However, a dearth of evidence exists exploring this association for other population groups, including cis-gender women (cis-women), although their knowledge, values and preferences for PrEP have previously been explored.^{14 15}

We will conduct a systematic review to explore the existing evidence on the association between daily oral PrEP use for the prevention of HIV and the incidence of bacterial STIs in cis-gender women. This exploration may provide insight for understanding strategies to control the spread of STIs among PrEP users and their sexual partners and identify priorities for future research and policy recommendations.

1.2 Research question

What is the association between pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) and the risk of bacterial sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among cis-gender women?

2 Methods

Design and methods for this systematic review are in accordance with the PRISMA guidelines for reporting systematic reviews.¹⁶

2.1 Information sources and search dates

- **Databases:** MEDLINE (via Ovid), EMBASE (via Ovid), Cochrane CENTRAL
- **Trial databases:** ANZCTR, ISRCTN, Open Trials, EU Clinical Trials Register, WHO ICTRP, clinicaltrials.gov, AVAC
- **Hand reviewed journals and conference databases:** CSA Conference Papers Index, Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections (CROI), International AIDS Conference (IAC), Conference on HIV Pathogenesis, Treatment and Prevention (IAS)
- **Search dates:** from creation to date of search

2.2 Search strategy

We will search databases for the concepts of: (1) HIV, (2) PrEP and (3) STIs and (4) women, reported in the latest articles and conference abstracts published – see Table below.

Adapted from Werner *et al*⁹ developed with a librarian and a researcher based at Imperial College London.

Ovid Database search

MEDLINE/EMBASE

	Search terms (including MeSH)
1	exp HIV infections/
2	exp HIV/
3	(hiv OR hiv1 OR hiv2 OR human immun* deficiency virus*).ab,ti,kw.
4	1 or 2 or 3
5	exp Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis/
6	PrEP.ab,ti,kw
7	((Preexposure OR Pre exposure) AND (prophylaxis OR chemoprophylaxis OR chemoprevention OR prevention)).ab,ti,kw.
8	Truvada OR tenofovir OR emtricitabine OR tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.ab,ti,kw.
9	5 or 6 or 7 or 8
10	exp Sexually Transmitted Diseases/
11	exp Sexually Transmitted Diseases, Bacterial/

12	(sexually transmitted infection* or sexually transmitted disease* or bacterial sexually transmitted infection* or syphilis or gonorrh?ea or chlamydia* or venereal disease*).ab,ti,kw.
13	10 or 11 or 12
14	exp Women/
15	exp Mother/
16	(wom#n OR female* OR mother*).ab,ti,kw.
17	14 or 15 or 16
18	4 and 9 and 13 and 17

Web of Science search

	Search terms
1	(hiv or hiv1 or hiv2 or human immun* deficiency virus)
2	(PrEP or Truvada OR TDF OR tenofovir OR emtricitabine or (Preexposure or Pre exposure) AND (prophylaxis or chemoprophylaxis or chemoprevention or prevention))
3	(sexually transmitted infection* or sexually transmitted disease* or bacterial sexually transmitted infection* or syphilis or gonorrh?ea or chlamydia* or venereal disease*)
4	(wom\$n OR female* OR mother*)
5	#1 and #2 and #3 and #4

Cochrane CENTRAL

	Search terms (including MeSH)
#1	MeSH descriptor: [HIV Infections] explode all trees
#2	MeSH descriptor: [HIV] explode all trees
#3	hiv:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#4	#1 or #2 or #3
#5	MeSH descriptor: [Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis] explode all trees
#6	MeSH descriptor: [Emtricitabine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate Drug Combination] explode all trees
#7	Pre-exposure prophylaxis:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#8	truvada:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#9	#5 or #6 or #7 or #8
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Sexually Transmitted Diseases] explode all trees
#11	MeSH descriptor: [Sexually Transmitted Diseases, Bacterial] explode all trees
#12	sexually transmitted infection*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#13	sexually transmitted disease*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#14	syphilis:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#15	gonorrh?ea:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#16	chlamydia*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#17	#10 or #11 or #12 or #13 or #14 or #15 or #16
#18	MeSH descriptor: [Women] explode all trees
#19	MeSH descriptor: [Mothers] explode all trees
#20	wom?n:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#21	female:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#22	mother:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#23	#18 or #19 or #20 or #21 or #22
#24	#4 and #9 and #17 and #23

2.3 Eligibility criteria

- Study design: Open-label randomised controlled trials, demonstration and implementation projects and observational studies (including cohort studies, cross-sectional)
- At least 3 months of follow-up reported with sufficient data to calculate person-years of follow-up
- Risk of bacterial STIs (e.g. incidence, prevalence) reported during follow-up, by intervention status
- Publication: Full text, peer-reviewed journal articles, conference abstracts or grey literature published in English
- Publication date: not limited
- Publication status: published and in progress
- Geographic location of studies: not restricted
- Exclusion: studies that relate to perceptions/acceptability/willingness to take PrEP, rather than actual PrEP use
- Exclusion: studies solely measuring HIV acquisition (and PrEP) rather than STI acquisition
- Exclusion: studies not meeting the PICO criteria (**Table 1**)

Table 1: PICO

Population	HIV-seronegative cisgender women, over 15 years old <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential sub-populations include HIV-seronegative women in serodiscordant relationships, female sex workers, adolescent girls and young women (AGYW)
Intervention	The use of PrEP for the prevention of HIV
Comparison	No PrEP use
Outcomes of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incidence or prevalence of bacterial STIs diagnoses (chlamydia, syphilis and gonorrhoea), including self-reported measures during follow-up • Treatment for bacterial STIs, including self-reported measures

2.4 Study records

2.4.1 Data management

EndNote to be used to manage references and Excel will be used to record details of studies included and excluded from review.

2.4.2 Study selection

Two independent reviewers (EC/VP) will search information sources and assess identified studies for inclusion. Titles and abstracts will be screened for eligibility using criteria listed in section 2.3 and subsequently full text screening of articles will occur. Any studies excluded from either of these steps will be noted. Bibliographies of relevant papers, government reports and other “grey literature”¹ will be scanned to check for articles missed by the initial search, a process referred to as “snowballing”. Any duplicate records will then be removed during screening.

Any disagreements between the two researchers (EC/VP) will be discussed and may involve a third and fourth researcher (BD/HW).

¹ Grey literature is literature produced by any organisation whose primary purpose is not publishing (e.g., government white papers, not-for-profit reports, dissertations/theses). The content and reference lists of evaluations of PrEP programmes will be scanned, including those conducted by government or public health organisations, conference abstracts, and trial registries. Where both conference abstracts and journal articles are reported (for the same study), the most recent publication will be included.

2.4.3 Data extraction

Using a standardised extraction template, two reviewers (EC/VP) will extract the data independently and record this within Excel. A third and fourth reviewer (BD/HW) will check the data for consistency.

Data items to be recorded include:

- Study design (and if clinical trial, trial design), geographic location and recruitment period
- Inclusion/exclusion criteria for participants in each study and sample size
- Participant demographics at baseline (e.g. age, race/ethnic group, sexual identity, socioeconomic variables, alcohol/drug consumption, STI prevalence)
- Length of follow-up and corresponding person-years of follow up
- Outcome measures: bacterial STI incidence (or prevalence) including diagnosis (syphilis, gonorrhoea, chlamydia), STI treatment (may be self-reported) during follow-up and at baseline
- Sexual behaviour (reported condom use, number of sexual partners, number of condomless partners)
- Assessment of study quality

If STI incident rates are unreported, prevalence rates will be reported or calculated by contacting authors (if possible) to obtain raw data, as described in previous studies.^{9 12}

2.5 Risk of bias

The quality of the cumulative evidence will be assessed using Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE).¹⁷

The third and fourth reviewers (BD/HW) will reconcile situations of disagreement.

2.6 Data

2.6.1 Synthesis

The summary table will include major study characteristics including:

- Citation information (including authors, date of study or publication)
- Study design and method
- Population studied
- Country/location
- Sample size
- Key findings/outcome measures (STIs and self-reported sexual behaviour)

Where available, STI incidence rates (per 100 person-years of follow-up) will be reported, by disease, with the 95% confidence interval for each study and presented on a forest plot. We will contact the primary author for raw data where sub-group analyses have not been completed or further statistical analysis is required.

The summary table will be checked, and refined once data extraction has begun.

2.7 Meta-bias(es)

A funnel plot will be used to detect publication bias. If publication bias is detected, the degree to which bias has occurred will be estimated.

A sensitivity analysis will be conducted to examine any potential effect due to the inclusion of conference abstracts.¹⁸

3 Dissemination and Timeline

3.1 Dissemination plan

- Late abstract submission for conference (ISSTD: 5 April; AIDSImpact: 17 June)
- Conference presentation
- PROSPERO
- Journal article publication
- Public channels (e.g. social media, blogs)
- Written evidence for policymakers

3.2 Proposed timeline

- **w/c 7 February:** development and finalisation of protocol
- **w/c 1 April 2019:** register protocol on PROSPERO
- **April 2019:** Literature search, quality appraisal and data extraction
- **April to May 2019:** Synthesis and write up
- **May 2019 onwards:** Dissemination (see above)

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